

Microsaccades & EEG alpha oscillations: A close relationship?

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Background

Microsaccades (MS) are small (< 1°) involuntary eye movements that occur at a rate of 1-2/s during attempted visual fixation (Fig. 1). MS have received much attention in the EEG community after it was shown that the myogenic **spike potential** at MS onset can contaminate the **gamma** (> 30 Hz) band (Yuval-Greenberg et al., 2008).

In contrast, we demonstrated at last ICON (2008) that MS are also a potentially strong source of genuine **cortical activity** scalp-recordable in the EEG. In particular, MS are followed by the **microsaccadic lambda response** (Fig. 2), an occipital peak after ~105 ms that is likely a P1-like visual potential triggered by the retinal image displacement (Dimigen et al., 2009; 2011). At least under some conditions, MS present a hidden source of brain signal that can influence the interpretation of stimulus-locked EEG/ERP data (Dimigen et al., 2009) and may also have functional relevance for stimulus processing.

In a visual oddball task, we also observed that MS were followed by a **damped oscillation** consisting of several cycles of **alpha band** (~10 Hz) activity over occipital cortex. This indicates a possible relationship between the generation of MS and the phase of alpha oscillations (an idea first proposed in the 1960ies), raising the following research questions:

1. Are alpha oscillations locked to MS a reliable observation in event-related EEG data?
2. If so, what is the causal direction of this relationship?

General Methods

Subjects

- age: 18-37, uncorrected good acuity (tested), mostly naive

Eye Tracking

- binocular pupil+CR tracking at 500 Hz with SMI HiSpeed column
- head-stabilized with chinrest (or dental impression bite-bar)

MS detection

- binocular outliers in 2-D velocity space (Engbert & Mergenthaler, 2006)
- threshold multiplier (VTHR): 4-5 SD; min. duration: 6 ms

Simultaneous EEG

- 12-64 electrodes sampled at 500 Hz, bandwidth 0.1 - 100 Hz
- average reference (linked mastoids in Busch et al. replication)
- time-locked to stimulus onsets & MS onsets

Sorted trials

- shown for occipital electrode Oz, vertical smoothing: over 40-180 trials

Time-frequency analyses

- 5-cycle Morlet wavelets to extract phase & power
- phase-locking index as measure of inter-trial & inter-MS coherence

Fig. 1. Fixational eye movements (MS in red)

Fig. 2. Microsaccade-locked ERP: Spike potential & visually-evoked MLR

1. MS-related alpha effects: A general phenomenon in event-related EEG data?

Visual oddball task (N = 12)
Dimigen et al. (2009, *J Neurosci*)

Classification of emotional words & faces (N = 24)
(data shown collapsed across emotions)

Detection of near-threshold stimuli (N = 3)
(replication of: Busch et al., 2009, *J Neurosci*)

2. What is the relationship between MS and alpha oscillations? Are MS entrained to alpha phase?

Two possible accounts

1. MS phase-reset ongoing alpha rhythm or evoke oscillation
2. MS are generated phase-locked to ongoing alpha cycle

Steady fixation on patternless background (N = 14)

- task: precisely fixate stationary stimulus for 10 s
- red fixation dot on grey background
- trial aborted in case of blink
- collected 20 - 40 successful trials per subject

- analyzed MS > 2 s after trial onset and > 1 s before offset
- excluded MS < 150 ms away from preceding MS
- n = 1,326 MS (29-163 per subject). Median amplitude: 0.36°

Permutation statistics

Time-frequency analyses were compared to TFAs computed on surrogate data. Surrogate data was generated for each subject by randomly reassigning the trial vector of observed MS latencies to different EEG fixation trials. TFA computed based on these artificial MS latencies yielded a distribution of power/PLI values expected under the null hypothesis. Data is shown as mean z-scores which are based on the surrogate distribution resulting from 200 random permutations per subject. Only z-values are shown that differ significantly ($p < .05$) from zero (t-tests across subjects).

Conclusions

Results from several typical event-related EEG paradigms confirm previous observations that most experimental trials contain **at least one microsaccade**.

Our results replicate previous findings that microsaccades are not only accompanied by a facial muscle spike, but also by a brain response over visual cortex that is overlaid on the stimulus-locked EEG. In addition, in three of the experiments, we found that the microsaccade-locked ERP contained a **damped oscillation** of around 10 Hz.

Microsaccade-sorted trials suggest that **post-stimulus alpha phase** at occipital electrodes is not only determined by the stimulation but **modulated** by the presence of **microsaccades**. Consequently, inter-trial phase coherence (relative to the stimulus) was lower in trials in which an additional microsaccade occurred in temporal proximity to the stimulus (i.e., early in the trial).

Prolonged fixation on a stationary patternless stimulus provided **no evidence** that microsaccades are themselves **entrained** to the occipital alpha phase: We found significant phase-locking after but not before microsaccades.

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